

Functional Form of Entropy Due to Physical Constraints? Part 4

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 5, 2025

In Part 3, we argued that entropy is an essential function because it deals with stability under fluctuations $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$. These fluctuations should occur in nature and one wishes a physical equilibrium scenario to be stable in their presence. When dealing with entropy, one often also discusses constraints. Here, we argue that these constraints represent conservation in the system, e.g. $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$. It is fine to have fluctuations, but these cannot increase particle number or total energy. As a result, in the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) case, one may create a math function $-p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ such that $p \rightarrow p+dp$ leads to 0 if the differentials of the two constraints are considered. This approach bypasses reaction balance altogether, while reaction balance $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_i)p(e_j)$ for $e_1+e_2=e_i+e_j$ bypasses entropy altogether. Yet, both results are the same. In this note, we try to delve into this issue.

In particular, we consider, like in Part 3, the Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) cases. In those cases as in the MB case, one may obtain the distribution $p(e_i)$ directly through reaction balance (and elastic scattering) with no need to consider entropy or fluctuations $p \rightarrow p+dp$. Physically, however, one requires stability with respect to these fluctuations as argued in Part 3. The question then becomes: What is entropy in such a case? Entropy is often described as the \ln of the number of states, but then in the drastic approximations made, it becomes more akin to average energy, at least in the MB case. In the FD and BE cases, however, matters are very different and so we suggest that these cases be studied. In particular, we suggest that one must consider fluctuations which respect conservation of quantities, but at the same time be aware of the physical statistical features present in the reactions which create the equilibrium (i.e. reaction balance). Thus, the entropy function is linked to both the differentials of the constraints of conserved quantities and to the features of reaction balance. In particular, one must capture these features of reaction balance in an accurate statistical manner, we argue. This then ultimately leads to the form of the entropy function. In the MB case, one cannot see this clearly because entropy mimics the energy constraint, but this is not a general feature which carries over to the FD and BE cases. In particular, we argue that entropy is a sum of the probability multiplied by information $\ln(p)$ for all physical probabilities which appear in a reaction balance equation.

The Maxwell-Boltzmann Case

One may obtain the MB distribution directly from reaction balance for elastic collisions:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_i)p(e_j) \text{ for } e_1+e_2 = e_i+e_j \rightarrow \ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \text{ or } p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((1))$$

The point we make is that there is no resort to maximizing an entropy function subject to constraints. There is no notion of fluctuations $p \rightarrow p+dp$ leaving the system invariant. The key physical idea is that $p(e_i)$ is the probability for a particle to react.

Alternatively, one may write an expression for \ln of the number of states:

$$\ln\{N! / \text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)!\} \quad ((2))$$

Using Stirling's approximation: $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$ one has:

$$- \sum \text{over } i \ p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad \text{if } n(e_i) = N p(e_i) \quad ((3))$$

((3)) is then maximized ($d/dp(e_i)$) subject to the constraints:

$$\sum \text{over } i \ p(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum \text{over } i \ e_i p(e_i) = e_{ave} \quad ((4))$$

and $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ again obtained.

In such an approach, there is no examination of the physical interactions present.

We stress that two seemingly unrelated and independent processes yield the same MB distribution. How can this be? We first note that Stirling approximation is drastic and that $\sum \text{over } i \ p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ is very similar to the energy constraint because $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. Thus, it seems that one could, under the approximations linked with the Stirling approximation, consider an a priori definition of entropy not directly linked to $\ln(\text{number of states})$. It is, however, also not correct to suggest that entropy is always equivalent to the energy constraint with $\ln(p) = -e_i/T$, as will be seen in the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases. This begs the question: What is entropy and how is it linked to reaction balance? Reaction balance is based on the key idea that $p(e_i)$ is the probability required for an e_i particle to take part in an interaction. In other words, examining an interaction statistically should reveal the physical probability or probabilities involved and these seem to be part of an entropy expression. In other words, in

$$- \sum \text{over } i \ p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((5))$$

$p(e_i)$ is not simply an averaging probability, but the probability which appears in a reaction. $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ is linked to the energy constraint, but as will be seen, the $-e_i/T$ piece may be formed from a sum of entropy terms and not a single term as in ((5)). Thus, we caution using the definition: average information = entropy too literally. This definition may be applied to the FD and BE cases, but there can be multiple probabilities. In probability theory, $\ln(\text{probability}) = \text{information}$. It is a coincidence that this information in ((5), $\ln(p(e_i))$), also happens to directly represent a key physical piece of information $-e_i/T$.

As a result, we consider the FD and BE cases.

Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein Cases

The Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases may be described through reaction balance as:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j \quad ((6a)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$p(e_1) (1 -/+ p(e_i)) p(e_2) (1 -/+ p(e_j)) = p(e_i) (1 -/+ p(e_1)) p(e_j) (1 -/+ p(e_2)) \quad ((6b))$$

We suggest that reaction balance is key to understanding the problem and one may in fact obtain both the FD and BE distributions directly from ((6a)) and ((6b)) without any resort to the notion of maximizing entropy subject to constraints of conserved quantities. Without considering fluctuations $p \rightarrow p+dp$, however, one cannot prove that one has a stable equilibrium. Even in mechanics there are unstable equilibrium situations and statistical unstable equilibrium is not of interest here.

As a result, we argue that one must use the information of the reaction balance equation ((6b)) in formulating an entropy expression whose variation with respect to $p(e_i)$ is equivalent to the differentials of the constraints of the conserved quantities.

The approach which seems to emerge is one linked with information science, namely considering:

$$\text{Information} = \ln(\text{probability}) \quad ((7))$$

The key is then to identify the probability or probabilities in the problem. One may write:

$$p(e_i) / (1 - p(e_i)) \quad ((8))$$

and treat ((8)) as a mathematical probability, but physically there are two probabilities:

$$p(e_i) \quad \text{and} \quad (1 - p(e_i)) \quad ((9))$$

We argue that it is the physical features which are essential and that one cannot simply use \ln of ((8)) as information. We also note that the two probabilities in ((9)) appear on opposite sides of the equation ((6b)). We propose creating a function which makes use of the average of both informations:

$$p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) + (1 -/+ p(e_i)) \ln(1 -/+ p(e_i)) \quad ((10))$$

Thus, $-e_i/T$ arises as a combination of $\ln(p(e_i))$ and $\ln(1 -/+ p(e_i))$ from two entropy terms. One may now extremize ((10)) and link it to the differentials of the two constraints (linked to conserved quantities) ((4))

Entropy seems to be essential because it shows one has stability under $p \rightarrow p+dp$, but one requires the reaction balance form to find the probabilities in question which are needed to create entropy as a sum of information ($\ln(p)$) pieces.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that reaction balance is key to creating an entropy function. One might argue that reaction balance for elastic collisions yields the distribution in question (MB,FD,BE), but it does not show that it is stable under fluctuations $p \rightarrow p+dp$. We are only interested in stable equilibria and so an entropy function is needed. Reaction balance demonstrates the physical probability or probabilities present in an interaction. Mathematically, one might combine these as in $p(e_i) / (1 \pm p(e_i))$ in the FD and BE cases, but physically they are separate probabilities and one should create information terms (as in $\ln(p)$) for each. Thus, in the MB case, there is one probability in reaction balance and so one writes: $p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$. It is a coincidence that $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. (Actually, this occurs because there is only one probability.) If there are two probabilities, as in the FD and BE cases, then one has: $p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \pm (1 \pm p(e_i)) \ln(1 \pm p(e_i))$. Thus, entropy seems to be a sum of information terms for each physical probability in a reaction balance equation. This entropy should then be stable to $p \rightarrow p+dp$, on other $d/dp(e_i)$ of the entropy function should yield the differentials of the constraints of the conserved quantities which sum to 0, i.e. $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$ and $\sum_i e_i dp(e_i) = 0$.